

Parents' Perceptions of the Health Services Provided for Students with Disabilities in Integrated Schools in Jordan

Mohammad A. Beirat

Al-Hussein Bin Talal University/Ma'an -Jordan
Faculty of Education Science, Department of Special Education,
ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8730-6405>

***Daniel L. Mpolomoka**

Unicaf University Zambia
School of Education, Humanities and Social Sciences,
ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2479-2693>
Email: mpolomokadl@gmail.com

Ahmad Algolaylat

Yarmouk University
College of Educational Sciences
Counselling and Educational Psychology Department
ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6261-4428>

Hussein Al Njadat

Tafila Technical University
College of Educational Sciences
Department of Educational Psychology
ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8545-1983>

*Corresponding author email: mpolomokadl@gmail.com

Abstract

Background: Students with disabilities attending integrated schools sometimes have several health issues that necessitate regular monitoring by healthcare professionals.

Objective: The study sought to assess the extent of healthcare services provided to students with disabilities in integrated schools in Jordan, as perceived by parents.

Methodology: The study used the descriptive approach and sampled 25 fathers and 23 mothers of integrated students. It adhered to strict inclusivity and exclusivity criteria. This included examining

the provision of services based on gender (fathers, mothers) and the specific category of disability integrated into schools (mental, hearing, physical, and health disabilities). The researchers developed the available health services scale, and its validity and reliability implications were demonstrated.

Results: The study findings indicated that the provision of health care was subpar, with a mean value of 2.04. Additionally, the study uncovered statistically significant variations in parents' responses based on the gender variable. The average of fathers' responses was 2.20, which was greater than the average of mothers' responses, which was 1.86. The study found no statistically significant differences in the responses of the study sample members based on the variable of the integrated student's disability category (mental, hearing, physical, and health disabilities) at a significance level of 0.413, indicating that the observed value is not statistically significant.

Conclusion: The study highlights the importance of healthcare in integrated schools by considering the specific needs of students with disabilities and incorporating the perspectives of parents.

Unique Contribution: The study has provided practical suggestions to enhance the quality of health services in integrated schools, including improving communication among service providers and increasing social support for students with disabilities and their families.

Key Recommendation: The study suggests enhancing awareness and collaboration between schools and families, formulating health policies, and offering vocational training for service providers as means to enhance the quality of life for students with disabilities in integrated schools.

Keywords: Health Services; Students with Disabilities; Integrated Jordanian Schools; Parents; Health Service Providers

Introduction

The Maternal and Child Health Office estimated that approximately 16% of students under the age of 18 experience chronic health conditions in the physical, developmental, behavioural, or emotional domains. The office also provided an inclusive definition of these conditions, which encompasses the additional health and related services needed by these students beyond what is required for those who develop typically. This was in addition to the increase in students afflicted with asthma and diabetes. This has a significant effect on expanding the provision of healthcare services for individuals with medical illnesses or those who rely on daily medical technology for their survival, including students with disabilities, who make up 1% of the total population of students with disabilities. These health services require the availability of a team of professionals working in community institutions and integrated schools that face challenges in meeting the educational and daily needs of students who suffer from health issues (Al-Bustanji, Bdour & Beirat, 2018; Mulambia et. al., 2023).

Sit, et. al. (2023) contend that children with disabilities need various health services in integrated schools. These services include health education, health promotion, preventive services, primary services, routine examinations to detect visual and hearing impairments, assessment of speech and language disorders, evaluation of physical and psychological objectives, provision of specialised diagnostic and treatment services, and healthcare services. The Federal Law known as NCLB

mandates that integrated schools must offer educational services to all students based on their individual abilities. These services, such as speech therapy, occupational therapy, and physical therapy, are provided when it is determined that students require them in order to benefit academically.

The characteristics of students with disabilities and their health fluctuations require the provision of daily health services in integrated schools through the school health program attached to each integrated school, as many of them are unable to communicate due to mental disabilities or linguistic or speech disorders. Consequently, families become responsible for conveying their children's needs, as effective communication between health service providers, students with disabilities, their families, and community resources is crucial in addressing their health needs within their integrated schools. This necessitated this study.

Theoretical Framework and previous studies

Efforts to improve health policies and services for children with disabilities are advancing globally, with school health programs playing a vital role in ensuring comprehensive care for students in integrated schools. The American Academy of Paediatrics (AAP) introduced the “medical home” framework, fostering collaboration between healthcare providers and parents of students with disabilities. This model incorporates accessible, ongoing, comprehensive, family-oriented, empathetic, and culturally sensitive services. It has significantly impacted students’ well-being by maintaining physical and mental health, supporting parents, and enhancing rehabilitation, health education, and coordination within integrated educational settings. The AAP also provides palliative services in integrated schools to address the physical, psychological, social, and spiritual needs of students and their families. This approach has improved students’ well-being and addressed family-specific requirements. However, challenges persist in delivering health services in integrated schools, such as financial constraints, inadequate communication, low parental satisfaction, and the increasing complexity of medical needs (Ianni et al, 2023; Paccaud et al, 2021). Despite these challenges, collaboration between healthcare providers and schools has improved monitoring and the quality of care for students with disabilities.

Studies have explored diverse aspects of health services in this context. Brown et al (2022) emphasised the investment in trauma-oriented services and their role in addressing the health consequences of trauma, while Maitre and Duncan (2023) emphasised the importance of monitoring development progress and integrating advanced technologies. Howren et al. (2023) examined factors contributing to interruptions in follow-up services, finding deficiencies in social support systems. Lindsay et. al. (2024) explored therapeutic interventions for individuals with impairments, aiming to enhance their effectiveness. Amidst the COVID-19, Dickinson et. al. (2023) highlighted the critical role of social support for students with disabilities in Australia, showing its significant influence on student engagement and well-being. Collectively, these studies underline the need for enhanced resources, communication and innovative strategies to sustain and improve health services for students with disabilities in integrated settings.

Study objectives

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Gain a comprehensive understanding of parents' views on health services available to students with disabilities in integrated schools in Jordan.
2. Determine parents' perception of health services provided in integrated schools for students with disabilities.

Study Terms

Health services: include all services and interventions designed to preserve or restore health, encompassing preventive health services, diagnosis, treatment, care and rehabilitation (World Health Organisation (WHO), 2020). In this study, 'health services' refer to the specific set of services that are expected to be provided in integrated schools. These are included in the measure used in the study, and parents were asked to respond to questions about them.

Students with disabilities: this term refer to students with mental, hearing, physical, or health disabilities that hinder their participation in standard education. The study examines parents' responses to health services provided in integrated schools, focusing on students facing such challenges (Chikopela et. al., 2022; International Classification of Functioning, 2011).

Jordan's integrated schools: integrated schools combine students with disabilities and typical students in the same classrooms, offering tailored support to promote inclusive and equal learning opportunities (Sikanyika et. al., 2022; Ministry of Education, 2023). This study focuses on integrated schools attended by students with cognitive, auditory, physical, and health-related impairments, whose parents participated.

Parents: Parents, whether biological, adoptive, or primary caregivers, play a vital role in the upbringing and well-being of students with disabilities, offering emotional, health and educational support (United Nations, 2024). This study focuses on parents' views on health service accessibility in integrated schools.

Health services providers: Healthcare providers, including doctors, nurses and health practitioners, deliver medical services to individuals and institutions (WHO, 2020). These professionals are responsible for the healthcare of students in integrated schools, managing treatments, palliative services, and other health needs.

Method

The researchers employed a descriptive approach (Mpolomoka, 2024), utilizing the survey method, to ascertain the extent of health services accessible to students with disabilities in integrated Jordanian schools. The study revealed this information from the perspective of parents, while also ranking the level of services based on variables like gender and the category of integrated disability.

The researchers carried out the following procedures to achieve the goal of the current study:

- 1) Study scale design: developed a scale to measure the availability of health services for students with disabilities in integrated schools, focusing on essential care needs, with thorough validity and reliability assessments.

- 2) Sample selection: A sample of parents was carefully selected who willingly and actively cooperated, and who have children with disabilities enrolled in integrated schools in Jordan.
- 3) Scale distribution and data collection: provided the parents participating in the study with the scale in a physical paper format and gathered pertaining to the accessibility of healthcare services as seen by parents.
- 4) Data analysis: analysed the data collected from the questionnaire using statistical methods appropriate for the purpose of the study.
- 5) Interpretation of the results: interpreted the results drawn from the analysis, and presented conclusions and recommendations based on the results.

Study Scale

The scale was developed based on literature on health services in integrated schools and studies by Adugna et al. (2020), Tetreault et al. (2014), and Janus et al. (2008). Standards from Jordan's Supreme Council for Disability Affairs were also reviewed. Faculty experts in special education and nursing evaluated the scale's relevance to students with disabilities, suggesting improvements. After revisions, 28 items were finalized to represent necessary health services, tailored for parental responses. The scale uses a five-point Likert format with its correction key determined according to standard scale rules. This is depicted in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Five-point Likert format

Not available	Scarcely	Sometimes	Mostly	Always
1	2	3	4	5

Based on the above, the values of the arithmetic means that were reached were based on the following equation:

For the upper value – the lower value of the answer alternatives divided by the number of levels, i.e., $5-1/3= 1.33$; this value is equal to the length of the category.

Thus, the low score ranges from 1.00 to 2.33;

The mean score ranges from 2.34 to 3.66;

The high score ranges from 3.67 to 5.00.

Internal consistency validity

After the procedure related to the accuracy of the arbitrators in preparing the scale, an internal consistency validity was conducted to increase reliability and confirm the validity of the scale. The Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated between the score of each statement and the total score of the scale. Table 2.0 shows the correlation coefficients of the items in the scale of health services, available in integrated schools, with the total score of the scale.

Table 2: The correlation coefficients of the items in the scale of health services

Paragraph	Correlation with the total score	Paragraph	Correlation with the total score
1	0.652*	15	0.428*
2	0.528*	16	0.564*

3	0.638*	17	0.601*
4	0.754*	18	0.615*
5	0.742*	19	0.493*
6	0.682*	20	0.529*
7	0.694*	21	0.734*
8	0.690*	22	0.706*
9	0.456*	23	0.701*
10	0.529*	24	0.624*
11	0.539*	25	0.491*
12	0.592*	26	0.549*
13	0.611*	27	0.586*
14	0.612*	28	0.625*

*Statistically significant at the level ($\alpha=0.05$)

Table 2 shows that all correlation coefficients of the items with the total score of the scale are statistically significant at the level of ($\alpha=0.05$), where the correlations of the items with the total score ranged between (0.428 and 0.754), and all of these values are statistically significant. This indicates the consistency of the internal structure of the scale. The measure of health services available in integrated schools consists of (28) items in its final form.

Reliability: is taken as a measure of health services available in Jordanian integrated schools, calculated using the Cronbach’s Alpha coefficient, and table 3.0 shows the reliability coefficient for the scale of health services available in integrated schools using the Cronbach’s Alpha method.

Table 3: Reliability coefficient for the scale of health services in integrated schools using the Cronbach’s Alpha method.

The scale	No. of paragraphs	Cronbach's Alpha reliability
Available health services	28	0.85

The data presented in Table 3 demonstrate that the reliability coefficient, as determined by the Cronbach alpha method, achieved a value of 0.85. This result indicates that the measure of health services available in integrated schools exhibits a high level of reliability. It is suitable for application to the sample of parents, as per the minimum reliability threshold of 0.70 set by Nanni’s scale (Shultz et al., 2020: 264-265).

Sample

The sample comprised 48 parents whose children were enrolled in schools with ages ranging from 7 to 15 years. The impairments encompassed in schools were primarily mental disabilities, hearing problems, physical and health limitations. The study sample was selected using a purposive approach, specifically from parents who willingly participated in applying the study scale. Table 4.0 displays the distribution of the study sample members based on their variables.

Table 4: Distribution of the study sample members based on their variables.

Item	Number	Percentage
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Parents gender	Fathers	25	52.1%
	Mothers	23	47.9%
	Total	48	100%
Disability category of the integrated student	Mental	16	33.3%
	Hearing	17	35.4%
	Health and physical	15	31.3%
	Total	48	100%

Statistical Treatments

Arithmetic means and standard deviations were used to answer the two questions of the current study which are appropriate for the purposes of the current study.

Results And Discussion

To reveal the health services available to students with disabilities in integrated Jordanian schools from the point of view of parents, the following questions were answered.

First: Results related to the answer to the first question, which is:

What is the level of availability of health services available in integrated schools in Jordan from the point of view of parents and what is their ranking?

In order to address this question, we computed the arithmetic means and standard deviations for the responses provided by parents of students with disabilities about the availability of health services in integrated Jordanian schools. These calculations are presented in table 5.0. The arithmetic means and standard deviations of the responses from parents of students with disabilities on the available health services scale are organised in descending order based on the arithmetic means.

Table 5: Arithmetic means and standard deviations of the responses of parents of students with disabilities on the available health services scale.

Rank		Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation	Degree
1	The school provides me with medical information related to my son's health problem.	2.83	1.06	Medium
2	My son takes into account the times of daily and monthly medication doses.	2.69	0.99	Medium
3	My son has a medical record at school that stores his medical examinations.	2.60	1.09	Medium

4	My son receives appropriate health services in case of seizures.	2.56	1.15	Medium
5	School health providers respect my son's feelings and discuss with him.	2.23	0.95	Low
6	The health services provided to my son help him manage his fears.	2.21	1.09	Low
7	My son receives the annual seasonal flu vaccine at his school.	2.17	1.04	Low
8	My son has treatment for urinary system problems.	2.10	1.21	Low
9	The school has appropriate medical procedures for the respiratory problems my son suffers from.	2.10	1.24	Low
10	There is medical equipment that my son needs at his school.	2.08	0.90	Low
11	My son has access to health services related to hearing loss.	2.06	1.17	Low
12	The health services provided to my son at school reduce financial costs and are appropriate for my economic situation.	2.04	1.03	Low
13	The health referral system is available in the school when necessary.	2.00	1.07	Low
14	I can easily discuss my son's health needs with the school.	1.98	1.00	Low
15	My son's school has a full-time resident doctor.	1.98	1.02	Low

16	My son receives palliative services at his school.	1.96	1.11	Low
17	I feel that the health services provided to my son eliminate the need for him to go to the hospital.	1.92	1.07	Low
18	My son reaches the health services room without difficulty.	1.90	1.02	Low
19	There is qualified medical staff at my son's school.	1.83	0.95	Low
20	The school provides awareness and health education related to communicable diseases and their complications for my son.	1.81	1.00	Low
21	My son receives the appropriate vaccination for his health at his school.	1.77	0.86	Low
22	There are regular appointments and times for follow-up with my son at school from the primary health services doctor.	1.77	0.93	Low
23	Health services are supervised by a part-time consultant physician.	1.75	0.93	Low
24	I feel that the school is aware of the side effects of the medication my son takes during his work.	1.65	0.89	Low
25	Primary health services are available in the event of an emergency injury to my son at his school.	1.63	0.89	Low
26	My son receives appropriate dental services and regular appointments at his school.	1.56	0.82	Low

27	My son is given daily treatment suitable for his digestive problems.	1.38	0.79	Low
28	It offers my son to measure his temperature, weight, and blood pressure.	1.10	0.59	Low
Total score for a measure of the availability of health services in integrated Jordanian schools.		2.04	0.31	Low

Table 5 illustrates that from the perspective of parents, the total arithmetic mean of health services provided to students with disabilities in integrated Jordanian schools was low, with an arithmetic mean of 2.04. The arithmetic means for the items varied from 1.10 to 2.83, with the paragraph that states, ‘my son takes into account the times of daily and monthly medication doses,’ ranked first with a mean of (2.83) and the paragraph that states, ‘the school provides me with medical information related to my son’s health problem’ ranked second with a mean of (2.69).

The paragraph stating that my son’s medical records are kept at school for his medical examinations rated third, with an average score of 2.60, suggesting a moderate level of significance. The paragraph describing my son's daily treatment for his digestive difficulties was ranked twenty-seventh out of all the paragraphs, making it the second to last. It had a mean score of 1.38, indicating a relatively low relevance level. The paragraph related to the measurement of my son’s temperature, weight, and blood pressure is rated twenty-eighth, with an arithmetic mean of 1.10, indicating a low level of significance.

Researchers attribute inadequate health services in integrated schools to parents’ lack of awareness about their significant and deficient policy implementation. Schools struggle with limited tools and resources, leading to imbalances in program awareness and parents favouring some services over others. Communication and coordination issues between schools and health providers further affect service accessibility and quality. These challenges stem from insufficient funding, inadequate allocation of financial resources and shortages in qualified healthcare staff, which hinder efficient service delivery. Administrative and bureaucratic obstacles also impede the provision of healthcare. Despite these issues, integrated schools play a critical role by offering comprehensive health information about students’ conditions, easing parents’ responsibilities, and fostering confidence in the schools’ ability to monitor students’ health. Their commitment is evident in precise medication administration and their focus on students’ well-being, highlighting the potential of integrated schools to provide high-quality health care when adequately supported.

The presence of medical records in schools significantly aids staff in monitoring students’ health and addressing specific needs, fostering parental trust and enhancing the student experience. However, parents often prioritise other services, such as medical information and pharmaceutical care, over basic medical services like daily treatments or routine checks. This reflects a deficiency in staff training and competencies, hindering effective service delivery. Ianni et. al., (2023)

Paccaud et. al. (2021) and Lindsay et al. (2024) highlight a decline in health service provision in schools, despite their critical importance for students with disabilities.

Results related to the answer to the second question:

Are there statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the availability of health services in Jordanian integrated schools from the point of view of parents due to the variables (parents’ gender, and the integrated student’s disability category)? Table 6.0 presents the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the parental responses regarding the health services provided in integrated schools for students with disabilities, as determined by the study’s variables.

Table 6: Arithmetic means and standard deviations of parental responses on health services provided in integrated schools for students with disabilities.

Variable	Item	Number	Arithmetic mean	Standard deviation
Parents gender	Fathers	25	2.20	0.29
	Mothers	23	1.86	0.22
Disability category of the integrated student	Mental	16	2.12	0.25
	Hearing	17	1.93	0.32
	Health and physical	15	2.09	0.34

The findings in Table 6 show significant variations in parents’ responses regarding health services in integrated schools, influenced by parents’ gender and the student's disability category. An ANOVA test, detailed in Table 7 confirms the significance of these differences in parents’ evaluations of available health services.

Table 7: Results of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) test on the scale of health services available in integrated schools

Variance source	Sum squares	Degree of freedom	Mean squares	F value	Significance level
Gender	1.158	1	1.158	16.801	0.000*
Disability category	0.124	2	0.062	0.902	0.413
Error	3.033	44	0.069		
Adjusted total	4.537	47			

*Significance level ($\alpha=0.05$)

Table 7.0 reveals significant gender-based differences in parental responses regarding health services in integrated schools, with fathers (average response: 2.20) expressing higher satisfaction than mothers (1.86). Statistical analysis supports this, showing a high F-value of 16.801 ($p=0.000$). fathers’ greater interaction with the school environment and differing expectations for health services influence their positive evaluations. Social and cultural factors, including societal roles and prior experiences, also shape parental perceptions. The quality of health services, as assessed

by parents, is influenced by personal engagement, cultural background, and interactions with schools and health service providers, impacting overall satisfaction.

Table 7.0 also shows no statistically significant differences in parental responses regarding health services in integrated schools based on students' disability categories ($F=0.902$, $p=0.413$). This is attributed to diverse students' needs and the equal availability of basic health services across all disability types, resulting in consistent evaluations of health care regardless of the disability category.

Constraints and limitations

Time constraints: The researchers conducted the study in the period between 10/16/2024 - 1/21/2024 during the first semester of the academic year 2023/2024.

Place constraints: This study was conducted in integrated schools for people with disabilities in the Kasbah of Ma'an Governorate in Jordan. They provide integration programs for students with disabilities.

Human constraints: The study examines the responses of parents sampled and factors that influence their level of health awareness and availability of health services in integrated schools attended by children with disabilities. These factors include their knowledge and understanding of these services; personal health experiences with their children; preferences and needs for their children's health services, and the level of social support provided by the school or local community.

Conclusion

The findings indicated that the provision of health care for students with disabilities at integrated schools in Jordan, as perceived by parents, was inadequate, suggesting the presence of obstacles in delivering these services. Furthermore, the study uncovered differences in how parents reacted to a range of health services offered in integrated schools, taking into account factors such as gender and the specific disability category of the integrated student. It is crucial to enhance the delivery of healthcare services to students with disabilities in integrated schools by implementing practical and efficient strategies to meet their needs and enhance their opportunities for success in social, health, and educational domains.

Recommendations

1. *Promoting awareness and guidance:* To raise awareness about the significance of offering comprehensive and suitable healthcare services to students with disabilities in integrated schools.
2. *Enhancement of communication and partnership:* It is crucial to strengthen communication and collaboration among schools, parents, and health service providers in order to better address needs and improve the students' experience.
3. *Formulating policies and programs:* Integrated schools should formulate health policies and programs by taking into account parents' feedback, assuring the delivery of appropriate and integrated services that cater to the requirements of children with disabilities.

4. *Training and professional development*: Health service providers and staff in integrated schools should be trained to enhance their comprehension of the needs of students with disabilities and how to provide the necessary support.
5. *Evaluation and follow-up on performance*: Integrated schools should conduct periodic evaluations of the quality and efficacy of health services, and efforts directed toward enhancing performance in accordance with feedback from parents and the school community.

References

- Adugna, M.B., Nabbouh, F., Shehata, S. & Ghahari, S. (2020). Barriers and facilitators to healthcare access for children with disabilities in low and middle income sub-Saharan African countries: a scoping review. *BMC health services research*, 20, 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-019-4822-6>
- Al-Bustanji, M., Bdour, N., & Beirat, M. (2018). Hysterectomy of girls with intellectual disabilities in Jordan: a family perspective. *International Journal of Learning and Development*, 8(1), 53-72. doi:10.5296/ijld.v8i1.12342
- Brown, T., Ashworth, H., Bass, M., Rittenberg, E., Levy-Carrick, N., Grossman, S., ... & Stoklosa, H. (2022). Trauma-informed care interventions in emergency medicine: a systematic review. *Western Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 23(3), 334. doi: 10.5811/westjem.2022.1.53674
- Chikopela, R., Ndhlovu, D., Mandyata, J.M., Mpolomoka, D.L. and Kasonde-Ng'andu, S. (2022). Enhancing teaching and learning of Open and Distance Learning (ODL) students with disabilities using digital technologies at university, Zambia. *European Journal of Open Education and E-learning Studies*, 7(1),1-14. <https://doi.org/10.46827/ejoe.v7i1.4119>
- Dickinson, H., Smith, C., Yates, S. & Tani, M. (2023). The importance of social supports in education: survey findings from students with disability and their families during COVID-19. *Disability & Society*, 38(8), 1304-1326. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09687599.2021.1994371>
- Howren, M.B., Christensen, A.J. & Pagedar, N.A. (2023). Examination of risk factors for discontinuation of follow-up care in patients with head and neck cancer. *Cancer Medicine*, 12(1), 631-639. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cam4.4944>
- Ianni, L., Camden, C. & Anaby, D. (2023). How can we evaluate collaborative practices in inclusive schools? Challenges and proposed solutions. *Journal of Occupational Therapy, Schools, & Early Intervention*, 16(3), 346-367. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19411243.2022.2054486>
- International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (2011). Children & Youth Version. Retrieved from: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/43737>
- Janus, M., Kopechanski, L., Cameron, R. & Hughes, D. (2008). In transition: Experiences of parents of children with special needs at school entry. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 35, 479-485. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-007-0217-0>
- Lindsay, S., Fuentes, K., Rangunathan, S., Li, Y. & Ross, T. (2024). Accessible independent housing for people with disabilities: A scoping review of promising practices, policies and interventions. *Plos One*, 19(1), e0291228. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0291228>
- Maitre, N.L. & Duncan, A.F. (2023). The Future of High-Risk Infant Follow-Up. *Clinics in Perinatology*, 50(1), 281-283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clp.2022.11.006>

- Ministry of Education (2023). Annual Report on Inclusive Education. Amman, Jordan: Retrieved from: <https://moe.gov.jo/user/login>
- Mpolomoka, D.L. (2024). Research Ethics in Post-Graduate Education: A Meta-Analysis. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 15(13), 26-33 <https://doi.org/10.7176/JEP/15-13-02>
- Mulambia, P., Mpolomoka, D.L., Chitondo, L. and Muyendekwa, L. (2023). An Analysis of Secondary School Learners' Psychological State in Written Texts. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, 7(5), 1595-1606. <https://doi.org/10.47772/IJRISS.2023.70622>
- Paccaud, A., Keller, R., Luder, R., Pastore, G. & Kunz, A. (2021, April). Satisfaction with the collaboration between families and schools—the parent's view. In *Frontiers in Education*, 6, p. 646878. Frontiers Media SA .<https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2021.646878>
- Shultz, K.S., Whitney, D. & Zickar, M.J. (2020). *Measurement Theory in Action: Case Studies and Exercises* (3rd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003127536>
- Sikanyika, S.F., Muvombo, M., Matimba, M., Chikopela, R., Mpolomoka, D.L. and Banda, F. (2022). Insights into the Value of Inclusive Education to both Children with and without Disabilities at Kabulonga Boys Secondary School in Lusaka, Zambia. *Journal of Education and Practice*. 13(35), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.7176/JEP/13-35-01>
- Sit, C.H.P., Capiro, C.M., Abernethy, B., McKenzie, T.L. (2023). Healthy People 2010. In: Maggino, F. (eds) *Encyclopedia of Quality of Life and Well-Being Research*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-17299-1_1274
- Tétreault, S., Blais-Michaud, S., Marier Deschênes, P., Beaupré, P., Gascon, H., Boucher, N. & Carrière, M. (2014). How to support families of children with disabilities? An exploratory study of social support services. *Child & Family Social Work*, 19(3), 272-281. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2206.2012.00898.x>
- World Health Organization. (2020). Improving access to healthcare. Retrieved from: <https://www.who.int/access-to-healthcare>
- United Nations (2024). *The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2024*. United Nations publication, Sales No. E.24.I.1.